

Barriers and Benefits to Online Learning among Special Education Undergraduates

Udeme Samuel Jacob, Jace Pillay, Bolanle Misitura Oyundoyin, John Olusegun Oyundoyin

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 05, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Barriers, Benefits, Online learning, Detractor, Optimism, Pragmatist</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6416145</p>	<p><i>This study sought to explore barriers and benefits toward adopting online instruction, the berries that prevent effective online learning identified as detractors, as well as benefits of implementing online learning, were categorised as optimism and pragmatist. One and eighty-four undergraduates in the Department of Special Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria participated in the study. The study had three factors which were loaded as detractors, optimistic and pragmatist. The instrument used for data collection was tagged "Barriers and benefits to online learning." The scale had 48 items rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree while the internal consistency of the scale was Cronbach's > 0.81 which indicated suitability for the study. The findings revealed that age cannot cause variation in undergraduates' online detractors, optimists, and pragmatists behaviour. There was no significant difference between male and female online optimists and online pragmatists (where $p > 0.05$), while there was a significant difference between male and female based on their online detractor $t(45.776) = -2.02$ where $p < 0.05$. Furthermore, the result show that there is no difference among the level groups concerning how they learn from the different sub-groups that make up online teaching and learning.</i></p>

Introduction

The global outbreak of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has disrupted undergraduate academic programs. Universities worldwide were forced to suspend the traditional classroom interaction during the early part of 2020, when little was known about the disease, and no effective treatment or vaccine was available. The negative impact of the measure intended to maintain social distance, prevent the virus from spreading and ensure the safety of students is significant (Muller et al. 2020, Wang & Dai, 2020). The decision to close schools is generally based on scientific data that during influenza virus pandemics, a lower social association among students is necessary to interrupt the spread of the virus (Abuhammad, 2020). Evidence on the effectiveness of closing schools and other measures for social distancing almost entirely comes from research undertaken on this measure during influenza outbreaks, and it has been shown in such outbreaks that school students drive virus transmission (Brooks et al., 2020; Hens et al., 2009). Universities had to find new ways to deal with this challenging situation to ensure the continuity of curriculum and learning, which was the transition to an online learning environment (OLE) to meet learner needs (Kamble, Gauba, Desai & Golhar, 2021).

Due to the severity of the situation caused by the COVID-19 outbreak, the only option was to transition to online learning (Mahyoob, 2020). Many institutions and learners rely on online learning platforms, so the transition to online learning has not been without challenges. Understanding online learning is critical for providing high-quality education and expanding learners' knowledge. Online learning refers to learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using various electronic devices with internet access (e.g., computers, laptops, smart phones) (Hamed, 2021). If adapted adequately to student's learning styles, such a platform could be a platform that makes the process of education more student-centred, creative, and flexible (Singh & Thurman, 2019). The quality of online learning is determined by many factors, including Internet connectivity, access to technology, session infrastructure, learner and faculty instructor participation and interaction (Kamble, Gauba, Desai & Golhar, 2021). A systematic review suggested that online learning for undergraduate health professions was equivalent and possibly even superior to traditional curriculum delivery methods (George et al., 2014). However, the high risk of bias among several included studies precluded the authors from drawing definitive conclusions. Therefore, this study aims to estimate the barriers and benefits of online teaching among undergraduates in the Department of Special Education to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Purpose of the study

This study intends to investigate the barriers and benefits to online learning among undergraduates. Three factors were assessed based on age, gender, and level of study of the sampled population. The factors that were assessed were:

Factor 1: Online detractors

Students face many structural barriers to online work. It would be better for them to conduct conventional university studies.

Factor 2: Online optimists

Doing university online has many benefits for students,

Factor 3: Online pragmatists

Doing online university has some advantages (mainly financial), but involves many practical problems

Literature Review

Online learning environment

Most authors describe online learning as access to learning experiences via technology (Conrad, 2002). Therefore, (Coogee & Floyd, 2015) argue that online learning can be presented in synchronous, asynchronous, or hybrid learning environments. Synchronous learning environments are those settings where learning occurs in real-time and might incorporate activities such as instructor lectures, collaborative activities, and student questions. Simamora (2020) argued that online learning can expand the range of courses available to students, especially for students living in rural or inner cities. It is an approach that can be adopted for teaching learners in their remote locations (Yusoff, 2008) which in turn eliminates face to-face contact (Jacob & Pillay, 2021). Online learning will likely enhance the teaching of technology skills by instilling technological literacy in academic learning content; and providing professional development opportunities lecturers, including mentoring and learning in scientific community colleges.

In addition, researchers view online learning as the flexibility of the classes (Fish, 2016; Horspool & Lange, 2012; Platt et al., 2014) because learning will take place at the convenience of learners without any form of distraction arising from family challenges or health problems (Dyrbye et al., 2009; Kokko et al., 2015). Smart and Cappel (2006), argue that the basis of effective online learning is comparable to the foundation of effective learning in general. (Means et al., 2009) argue that online learning is defined as learning that takes place partially or entirely over the Internet. This definition excludes purely print-based correspondence education, broadcast television or radio, video conferencing, video cassettes, and stand-alone educational software programs. Oliver (2001) found that teaching online is a vastly different process from conventional teaching. It usually involves changes in both pedagogy and teaching practices.

For online teaching to become mainstream, it is necessary for institutions to ensure that their teachers have appropriate skills and expertise in not only the delivery of online courses and programs but also their design and development. According to Albrahim (2020), online teaching competencies and talents must be determined to help format expert improvement packages for online instructors. These capabilities and competencies are classified into six categories: (a) pedagogical skills, (b) content skills, (c) plan skills, (d) technological skills, (e) management and institutional skills, and (f) social and conversation skills. Online teaching can use these sets of competencies to self-evaluate their capabilities to educate online and pick out their education needs.

Barriers to online learning

A considerable amount of literature has been published on online learning barriers resulting in the underutilization of online learning resources in developing countries. These barriers include poor access to the Internet, upgrading network, updating resources such as software and lack of the ability and confidence resulting from shortage of training courses (Cheok, Wong, Ayub, & Mahmud, 2017; Hechter & Vermette, 2013). In a report by Muilenburg and Berge (2005) eight barriers faced by students in using online learning were identified. These barriers include administrative routine issues, academic skills, social interaction, cognitive and technological skills, encouragement, time and support for studies, inadequate and outdated resources, cost and access to the Internet, and several technical difficulties. Delays in instructors' responses, the limited number of technicians, high degrees of technology dependence, and high student frustration are other barriers that have also been reported by students (Navarro, 2000; Simonson et al., 2009).

In addition, Dabaj (2011) conducted a study entitled "Analysis of communication barriers to distance education". He divided the barriers into two main categories: the first lies at the unhidden barriers such as lack of expertise with technology, cost of communication and website access and second the hidden barriers that include resistance to new technology, fear from technology and rigid belief in traditional education. Similarly, by naming the barriers from learners' perspectives, Ardichvili (2008) found different results as (1) interpersonal factors – for example, fear of criticism and fear of misleading others; (2) procedural factors – that is lack of clarity on the best way of sharing, etc.; (3) Technological factors – such as lack of technological aptitude; and being different in other studies, the researcher had discovered the impact of (4) cultural factors – for example saving face, in-group orientation, etc. Other barriers were commonly reported in the previous studies like; time-

consuming, technical issues and organizational beliefs or cultural beliefs (Fish & Gill, 2009; Hartmann, Braae, Pedersen & Khalid, 2017).

Regarding barriers to online, they envelop vagueness, quality, assets, showing the procedure, and assessment. Some of the barriers faced by schools include hierarchical and basic elements. Quadri, Muhammed, Sanober, Qureshi, and Shah (2017) examined barriers influencing the usage of online learning environments. The barriers were classified into four categorised students, teachers, curriculum, and schools. The findings revealed that foundation and innovation are the most important barriers while the least noteworthy are understudies. Their results further indicated that a restricted opportunity to create instructional content was the greatest factor that prevented the execution of online learning, while the absence of ICT aptitudes is the least significant factor. Hadijah and Shalawati (2017) investigated barriers experienced **by educators** when utilizing online. They noted that time to set up an exercise utilising innovation was a significant barriers experiences by teachers. Other barriers were the absence of sufficient expert improvement concerning innovation, constrained physical assets, insufficiency of assets, restricted access to innovation, absence of specialized help, capability, and certainty. Students also viewed technical problems as one of key barriers to online learning (Song, Singleton, Hill, & Koh, 2004).

Benefits of online learning

A few studies have explored learners' perspectives of online learning particularly in terms of perceived strengths, Wu, Yen, and Marek (2011) have conducted a study about how the online learning boosting both of ability and confidence among EFL students. The sample of the study consisted of 227 non-major EFL learners from the business school of a technical university in central Taiwan. The results of the study showed some positive points. In a qualitative study, Petrides (2002) interviewed learners to obtain their perspectives on Web-based learning. When interviewed, some participants indicated that they tended to think more deeply about the subject areas when responding in writing as compared to giving verbal responses. They explained that they were able to continually reflect upon each other's reflections because of the public and permanent display of the discussion postings on the Web. As stated by one participant: "There is something that forces you to think more deeply about subject areas when you have to respond in writing" (Petrides, 2002, p. 72).

Convenience is another advantage identified in the online learning literature. For example, in Poole's (2000) study of student participation in a discussion-oriented online course, the results indicated that students participated in online discussions at times most convenient to them, such as on Saturdays. Poole also found that students mostly accessed course materials from their home computers, the place most convenient to them. Murphy and Collins (1997) found similar results in their study of communication conventions in instructional electronic chats. Participants indicated they read and responded to comments in online discussions at times convenient to them (e.g., early morning, late evening). Flexibility is another reported strength of online learning (Schrum, 2002). Petrides (2002) stated that participants reported it was easier to work in collaborative groups in an online course without rearranging everyone's schedule as one might do in a traditional face-to-face course. Additionally, students valued the flexibility of online learning and opportunities to communicate with teachers and peers in online learning settings (Klingner, 2003, McCall, 2002, National Centre for Vocational Education Research, 2002).

In Vonderwell's (2003) study some participants expressed that the asynchronous environment allowed them to write carefully about their ideas. For example, one participant stated: "the discussion questions were not just for writing the answers; they required reflection" (p. 86). Interaction has been highlighted as one of the keys to the success of Internet-based distance education (Picciano, 2002). While some researchers have suggested that online learning may allow for higher levels of interaction than the large lecture classes typical of business schools (Hay, Hodgkinson, Peltier, & Drago, 2004) as well as integrating those who might not normally participate in a traditional classroom (Mills & Salloway, 2001). It has been observed that online discussions in asynchronous learning environments foster students' in-depth information processing and critical thinking by allowing them the time to process their thinking when they post a message in online conferences (Duffy, Dueber, & Hawley, 1998).

Frith (2002) studied the effects of conversation on the learning outcomes of online nursing students. She found that instructional support in the form of online communications between the instructor and students or among peers using chat room, electronic mail, and discussion groups enhanced students' motivation and satisfaction with the class. Additionally, Benbunan-Fich and Hiltz (1999) found that groups participating in an asynchronous learning environment were able to produce better and longer solutions to case studies than the students who participated in in-class discussions; however, they were less satisfied with the interaction process. Henson, Kennett, and Kennedy (2003) also reported that asynchronous discussions were effective in facilitating case studies in online

Method

Participants

The study participants were undergraduates in the Department of Special Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria. The students in the Department completed an online form during the second-semester lectures and having had first online while the second-semester classes was held using both convention and online learning environment. The sample comprised 184 students: 85 male and 99 female students in the Department of Special Education. Most of the students do not have any previous experience with online learning. All first semester courses were conducted online during the first semester, while the convention and the online learning mode was adopted during the second semester, depending on class sizes.

Research Methodology

Compared to studies conducted solely using qualitative or quantitative methods, mixed-method studies provide a better and broader understanding of a problem (Hurmerinta-Peltomaki and Nummela, 2006). This integration also gives readers more confidence in the findings and conclusions drawn by researchers (O'Cathain et al., 2010). The first focus of this research is on the barriers to and benefits of online learning. With the help of Exploratory Factor Analyses, an adaptation of Berge's framework (2005) is used to confirm barrier and benefits to online learning. Using Regression Binary Logistic, the researchers want to see a link between perceived online learning barriers and benefits to their future decision. In this study, the researchers will delve deeper into the learners' explanations for their extreme ratings, as well as any potential barriers or benefits. In the search for new factors impeding the decision to continue future online courses, the triangulation of both quantitative and qualitative results is hoped to provide an overview of the prospect of online learning and its obstacles.

Ethical consideration

Informed consent was taken digitally from all the participants. Respondents' data was kept anonymous as no names were asked.

Method of data analysis

Categorical variables were reported as counts and percentages. Group comparisons were made with the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test keeping gender, level of study and age range as variables to find if there is any significant relationship between the barriers and benefits faced by the undergraduates. Correlation between variables was evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Results and Discussion

Result

Factor analysis

Items	Detractors	Optimists	Pragmatists	Items	Detractors	Optimists	Pragmatists
1		0.453		24			0.485
2				25		0.359	
3				26	0.486		
4	0.393			27	0.728		
5		0.587		28			0.471
6	0.397			29		0.361	
7		0.35		30		0.429	
8	0.449			31	0.458		
9				32			0.644
10		0.391		33		0.488	
11			0.7	34		0.523	
12			0.415	35			0.48
13			0.355	36		0.406	
14		0.47		37		0.574	
15			0.411	38			0.4
16		0.422		39	0.363		
17	0.356			40	0.673		
18			0.619	41		0.525	
19			0.468	42	0.442		

20	0.606	43	0.375
21			
22	0.599		
23	0.537		

Factor loading is a scale reduction process used to categorize number of items into groups and the minimum value for acceptable item loading is 0.30. Meanwhile, from the total of 43 items in the instrument, three factors loaded which has been labelled as online detractors (barriers), online optimists (benefits), and online pragmatists. Online detractors has 4, 6, 8, 17, 22, 23, 26, 27, 31, 39, 40 and 42 loaded on it, items 1, 5, 7, 10, 14, 16, 20, 25, 29, 30, 33, 34, 36, 37, 41 and 43 loaded under online optimists while items 11, 12, 13, 15, 18, 19, 24, 28 and 32 loaded in online pragmatists whereas items 2, 3, 9, and 21 do not load on any of the factors at all.

Research Question 1: Can age cause variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists?

Test of homogeneity of variance for an online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractors based on age groups

Test of Homogeneity of Variances					
	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	F	Sig.
Online Optimists	0.06	3	138	0.981	
Online Pragmatists	0.512	3	138	0.675	
Online Detractor	0.52	3	138	0.669	

Shows that online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractor have homogeneity of variance since the significant value for the three variables is greater than 0.05 which means the null hypothesis for the assumption which states that there is no significant homogeneity of variance for the variables and since the significant level is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that age cannot cause variation in students' online optimists, detractors, online pragmatists behaviour.

Analysis of variance for an online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractors based on age groups

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Online Detractors	Between Groups	0.14	1	0.1398	0.262	0.61
	Within Groups	74.80	140	0.5343		
	Total	74.94	141			
Online Optimists	Between Groups	0.48	1	0.4765	0.896	0.346
	Within Groups	74.46	140	0.5319		
	Total	74.94	141			
Online Pragmatists	Between Groups	0.08	1	0.0757	0.141	0.707
	Within Groups	74.86	140	0.5347		
	Total	74.94	141			

Shows that there is no significant difference between students with different age group (16 – 20, 21-25, 26-30 and 30 and above) as online optimists with $F_{(1, 140)} = 0.896$, online pragmatists with $F_{(1, 140)} = 0.141$ and online detractors with $F_{(1, 140)} = 0.262$ and $p > 0.05$. Therefore, it means there is no difference among the age group concerning how they learn from the different sub-groups that make up online teaching and learning.

Research Question 2: Would gender cause variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists?

Descriptive analysis of gender, based on online optimist, online pragmatists, and online detractor

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Online Optimists	Female	107	34.36	8.691	0.84
	Male	35	32.94	6.97	1.178
Online Pragmatists	Female	107	27.23	7.109	0.687
	Male	35	28.63	8.872	1.5
Online Detractor	Female	107	22.76	5.871	0.568
	Male	35	25.8	8.256	1.396

Shows that females are a bit better than their male counterparts as online optimists while males are better in online pragmatists and online detractors.

Independent t-test analysis of online optimist, online pragmatist, and online detractors based on gender

+Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means			
	F	Sig.		T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Online Optimists	Equal variances assumed	1.2	0.275	0.873	140	0.384	
	Equal variances not assumed			0.976	71.447	0.332	
Online Pragmatists	Equal variances assumed	3.38	0.068	-0.946	140	0.346	
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.846	49.087	0.402	
Online Detractor	Equal variances assumed	7.42	0.007	-2.393	140	0.018	
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.02	45.776	0.049	

Shows that online optimists and online pragmatists have homogeneity of variance since the significant value for the two variables is greater than 0.05 which means equal variance can be assumed with the assumption fulfilled whereas online detractor does not have homogeneity of variance since its significant value is less than 0.05 meaning equal variance cannot be assumed since the assumption has been violated. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female as online optimist $t(140) = 0.873$ and online pragmatists $t(140) = -0.946$ with $p > 0.05$ while there is significant difference between male and female based on their online detractor $t(45.776) = -2.02$ where $p < 0.05$.

Research Question 3: Would there be variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists based on their levels?

Test of homogeneity of variance for an online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractors based on levels

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Online Optimists	0.101	3	138	0.96
Online Pragmatists	1.163	3	138	0.326
Online Detractor	0.75	3	138	0.524

Shows that online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractors have homogeneity of variance since the significant value for the three variables is greater than 0.05 which means the null hypothesis for the assumption which states that there is no significant homogeneity of variance for the variables and since the significant level is greater than 0.05 then the hypothesis will be rejected which means there is significant homogeneity of variance.

Analysis of variance for an online optimists, online pragmatists, and online detractors based on level

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Online Detractors	Between Groups	1.25	1	1.248	1.168	0.282
	Within Groups	149.55	140	1.068		
	Total	150.80	141			
Online Optimists	Between Groups	0.03	1	0.035	0.032	0.857
	Within Groups	150.76	140	1.077		
	Total	150.79	141			
Online Pragmatists	Between Groups	2.81	1	2.812	2.66	0.105
	Within Groups	147.98	140	1.057		

Total	150.79	141
-------	--------	-----

Shows that there is no significant difference between students with different level group (100, 200, 300 and 400) as online optimists with $F_{(1, 140)} = 0.032$, online pragmatists with $F_{(1, 140)} = 2.66$ $p > 0.05$ and online detractors with $F_{(1, 140)} = 1.168$ and $p > 0.05$. Therefore, it means there is no difference among the level group concerning how they learn from the different sub-groups that makes up online teaching and learning.

Research Question 4: Is there a main and interaction effect of gender, age, and levels on online teaching and learning?

Test of equality of variance in online teaching and learning based on gender, level, and age group

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances				
F	Df1	df2	Sig.	
0.832		24	117	0.69

Shows that online teaching and learning has homogeneity of variance since the significant value is greater than 0.05 which means the null hypothesis for the assumption states that there is no significant homogeneity of variance for the variables and since the significant level is greater than 0.05 then the hypothesis will be rejected which means there is significant homogeneity of variance.

Two-way analysis of variance of main and interaction effect of gender, level, and age group on online teaching and learning

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects									
Source	Type III Squares	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Squared	
Corrected Model	8181.469a		24	340.895	1.553	0.064		0.242	
Intercept		273010	1	273010	1244.13	0.000		0.914	
Gender		570.663	1	570.663	2.601	0.110		0.022	
Level		833.164	3	277.721	1.266	0.289		0.031	
Age		684.107	3	228.036	1.039	0.378		0.026	
Gender * Level		258.63	3	86.21	0.393	0.758		0.01	
Gender * Age		1074.26	2	537.132	2.448	0.091		0.04	
Level * Age		1780.47	7	254.353	1.159	0.332		0.065	
Gender * Level * Age		1545.17	4	386.292	1.76	0.142		0.057	
Error		25674.3	117	219.439					
Total		1062017	142						
Corrected Total		33855.8	141						

a R Squared = 0.242 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.086)

Shows that there is no significant main effect of gender $F(1) = 2.601$, level $F(3) = 1.266$ and age-group $F(3) = 1.036$ with $p > 0.05$ on online teaching and learning, which shows that neither gender, academic level nor age group has a significant effect on online teaching and learning as gender only had 2.2% effect, academic level with 3.1% while age group has 2.6%. Also, there is no significant interaction effect of gender and academic level with $F(3) = 0.393$, gender and age group $F(2) = 2.448$ and academic level and age group $F(7) = 1.159$ with $p < 0.05$. The first order interaction effect of gender and academic level is 1%, gender and age group is 4%, while academic level and age group is 6.5%. Meanwhile, the second-order interaction effect of gender, academic level and age group $F(4) = 1.76$ with $p > 0.05$ also does not significantly affect online teaching and learning. The effect size of this second-order interaction is 5.7%. Thus, the variables considered in this present study do not explain the online learning behaviour of undergraduates because the combined effect of the adjusted $R^2 = 0.242e$, which is 24.2%.

Discussion of findings

First and foremost, the study has certain limitations due to its sample size. They are not only small, but they are not statistically representative of students in each University in the whole country. In addition, these data are based on self-declarations of competencies. Nevertheless, given the low frequency of quantitative comparative studies of undergraduates' attitudes to online learning, these results suggest further investigation in future studies that include more extensive, more representative samples.

In this study, factors related to a delayed response by teachers, a limited number of technicians, and a high degree of technology dependency were identified as barriers to online learning, which is consistent with the submission of (Navarro 2000; Simonson et al., 2009). Other barriers identified are time-consuming, technical issues and organizational beliefs or cultural beliefs (Fish & Gill, 2009; Hartmann, Braae, Pedersen & Khalid, 2017), poor access to the Internet, upgrading the network, updating recourses such as software and lack of the ability and confidence resulting from shortage of training courses (Cheok, Wong, Ayub, & Mahmud, 2017; Hechter & Vermette, 2013) which are consistent with the findings the present finding. These barriers have been classified into four according to Quadri, Muhammed, Sanober, Qureshi, & Shah (2017), which are students, teachers, curriculum, and school. Furthermore, factors related to the benefits of online learning identified in this study include flexibility (Schrum, 2002), ease of working in a group during online learning without rearranging everyone's schedule as it is the usual practice in a conventional learning environment (Petrides, 2002). Such benefits are the value students place on the flexibility of online learning and opportunities to interact with teachers and peers in online learning settings (Klingner, 2003, McCall, 2002, National Centre for Vocational Education Research, 2002).

The results show that age did not cause variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists behaviour. Chyung (2007) found that variation in the online conduct of older and younger students, but this study did not find variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists behaviour. DiBiase and Kidwai (2010) found that adults spent more time communicating online and logged in to the learning management system longer than the relatively younger undergraduate students. Moreover, Anshari et al. (2017) revealed that students use smartphones as a learning aid due to their convenience, portability, comprehensive learning experience, multiple sources, multitasking, and environmental friendliness, which may account for the indifference observed in the present result.

Gender cause variation in students' online optimists, online detractors, and online pragmatists. The results revealed that the relationship between females and online optimists was positive while males had a positive relationship with online pragmatics, but the two were insignificant. Pessimists anticipate adverse outcomes in their lives, while optimists tend to predict favourable results (Carver et al., 2010). This shows that females in the present study will likely expect a better result from online learning. Considering that females value, or value more than a domain, to attain their desired goal for online learning, they will show enthusiasm and an increased interest in that domain to achieve this goal (Carver & Scheier, 2001). A lack of motivation and a lack of engagement with goal-directed efforts result from being doubtful about online learning to achieve a goal. The female optimism construct may be modified due to its dispositional nature (Rand, 2009), as expectations are essential (Scheier & Carver, 2009; Scheier, Carver & Bridges, 2001).

On the other hand, male pragmatics online behaviour implies that they believe that life is dynamic which is subjected to constant change; hence the aims of online learning are bound to be emotional. The latest findings have been reported by Anshari et al. (2017). In other studies, the portability of smartphones has enabled users to capture everything from written notes to entire lectures using the camera. Meanwhile, some things that keep teachers from encouraging the use of smartphones in class include disruptions, the difficulty of learning face-to-face activities, cheating, and the effect text messaging services have on students' writing (Wali and Omaid 2020). However, online pragmatism and optimism were positively related to males and females respectively but did not significantly correlate with gender differences. The present findings align with several studies that found no differences between males and females regarding their learning outcomes in online courses (Astleitner & Steinberg, 2005; Yukselturk & Bulut, 2007). This study agrees with Little-Wiles et al. (2014) research is aligned with the analysis of Beer, Clark, and Jones (2010) which demonstrates that there is a shortage of gender gaps in grades in which male students do marginally better. At the same time, others have found that females perform significantly better than men (Chyung, 2001; Gunn, McSporran, Macleod, & French, 2003; Price, 2006; Rovai & Baker, 2005; Sullivan, 2001; Taplin & Jegede, 2001). The assumption that online learning is a means of providing education to many people quickly and at a lower cost is shared by males (Yukselturk & Bulut, 2007) is consistent with the present findings.

They consider that females had high optimist variance, which indicates benefiting from online learning. This aligns with Yukselturk and Bulut (2007), who reported that females view online communication as an opportunity for fostering greater collaboration in education. They more readily accept networks that improve group communication and learning. Although males were more stable in attitudes than females and were better at engagement, no significant gender differences were found in learning outcomes (Nistor, 2013). Learning satisfaction among online millennial learners was also not influenced by gender differences (Harvey et al., 2017). According to Berge and Giles (2008), e-learning enables learners to deliver learning tailored to their

specific needs just in time. It is essential to conduct further studies considering the inconsistent findings. The results of the present study show a positive relationship between female and online optimist behaviour. According to the study, grade level did not affect students' online optimists, detractors, and pragmatists. The reason for this may be the flexibility and opportunities for communication with teachers and peers that online learning provides (Klingner, 2003, McCall, 2002, National Centre for Vocational Education Research, 2002). From Vonderwell (2003), based on an online study behaviour of learners, one participant stated: "there was more to the discussions than just writing assignments; thinking about them was essential." Online-based learning has succeeded due to the interaction of instructors and students (Picciano, 2002).

Conclusion

For online courses or programs to be designed according to the needs of online learners, it is necessary to examine the characteristics of successful online learners. Thus, to develop high-quality online courses, researchers need to determine what will help students succeed. As a result, this study concentrated on two primary goals for online student success. First, we aimed to determine the relationship between student characteristics and success in online learning. In the second objective, instructors provided feedback on the course outcomes. This paper presents a discussion platform for the barriers and benefits of online learning on undergraduates based on age, gender, and level of study. To facilitate the transfer of necessary skills to all participants, regardless of gender, age, or level, participants in future study should be increased to get a more generalizable results about barriers and benefits of online learning. Research into who learns best and how this new approach to teaching and learning can be beneficial for everyone should be pursued as significant investments in hardware, software, and time have been made by both the institution and the student. Moreover, it is of utmost importance for school administrators to reflect on the main difficulties undergraduates encountered in adapting to online learning and develop relevant interventions to better harness the benefits (optimist and pragmatist) of online learning. For example, the infrastructural expansion will help ensure that no student is excluded from online lessons. At the same time, workshops can be organised for faculty members to be effective in using online tools and technologies.

Acknowledgements or Notes

The authors acknowledge the respondents to the research questionnaire

Funding

This work was supported by the South African Research Chairs Initiative of the Department of Science and Innovation and National Research Foundation of South Africa. South African Research Chair, Education and Care in Childhood, Faculty of Education, University of Johannesburg South Africa [grant number: 87300, 2017].

References

- Abuhammad S, Khabour OF, Alzoubi KH. COVID-19 Contact-Tracing Technology: Acceptability and Ethical Issues of Use. Patient Prefer Adherence. 2020; 14:1639-1647 <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S276183>
- Albrahim, F. A. (2020). Online teaching skills and competencies. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 19(1), 9–20.
- Anshari, M., Almunawar, M. N., Shahrill, M., Wicaksono, D. K., & Huda, M. (2017). Smartphone's usage in the classrooms: Learning aid or interference? *Education and Information Technologies*, 22(6), 3063–3079. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9572-7>
- Ardichvili, A. (2008). Learning and knowledge sharing in virtual communities of practice: Motivators, barriers, and enablers. *Advances in developing human resources*, 10(4), 541-554. <https://doi.org/10.1177/152342230831953>
- Astleitner, H., & Steinberg, R. (2005). Are there gender differences in web-based learning? An integrated model and related effect sizes. *AACE Review (formerly AACE Journal)*, 13(1), 47– 63. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/18902/>
- Bear, C. Clark, K., & Jones, D. (2010). Indicators of engagement. In C.H. Steel, M.J. Keppell, P. Gerbic & S. Housego (Eds.), *Curriculum, technology & transformation for an unknown future*. Proceedings ascilite Sydney 2010 (pp.75-86). <http://ascilite.org.au/conferences/sydney10/procs/Bear-full.pdf>
- Berge, Z. L. & Giles, L. (2008) 'Implementing and sustaining e-learning in the workplace', *International Journal of Web - Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*, 3: 3, 44-53. <https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/article/3012#pnlRecommendationForm>
- Benbunan-Fich, R. & Hiltz, S.R. (1999) Educational applications of CMCS: Solving case studies through asynchronous learning networks *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 4 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.1999.tb00098.x>

- Brooks, S. K., Smith, L. E., Webster, R. K., Weston D., Woodland L., Hall I, & Rubin G J. (2020) The impact of unplanned school closure on children's social contact: rapid evidence reviews. *Euro Surveill.*; 25(13): pii=2000188. <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.13.2000188>
- Carver, C. S., & Scheier, M. F. (2001). Optimism, pessimism, and self-regulation. In E. C. Chang (Ed.), *Optimism and pessimism: Implications for theory, research, and practice* (pp. 31-51). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Carver, C. S., Scheier, M. F., & Segerstrom, S. C. (2010). Optimism. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 30(7), 879-889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2010.01.006>
- Cheok, M., Wong, S., Ayub, A., & Mahmud, R. (2017). Teachers' perceptions of e-Learning in Malaysian secondary schools. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 5(2), 20-33.
- Chyung, S. Y. (2007). Age and Gender Differences in Online Behavior, Self-Efficacy, and Academic Performance. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 8(3), 213-222. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/106649/>.
- Close L. Song, E.S. Singleton, J.R. Hill, M.H. Koh (2004) Improving online learning: Student perceptions of useful and challenging characteristics. *Internet and Higher Education*, 7 (1), 59-70 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2003.11.003>
- Conrad, D. (2002). Deep in the hearts of learners: Insights into the nature of online community. *Journal of Distance Education*, 17(1), 1-19.
- Coogle, C., & Floyd, K. (2015). Synchronous and Asynchronous Learning Environments of Rural Graduate Early Childhood Special Educators Utilizing Wimba and Ecampus. *MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 11(2), 173-187.
- Dabaj, F. (2009). The role of gender and age on students' perceptions towards online education case study: Sakarya University, vocational high school. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(2), 120-123.
- DiBiase, D. & Kidwai, K. (2010). Wasted on the young? Comparing the performance and attitudes of younger and older US adults in an online class on geographic information. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 34(3), 299-326. https://www.e-education.psu.edu/sites/default/files/JGHE_DiBiase_Kidwai_2010.pdf
- Duffy, T.M. Dueber, B. & Hawley, C.L. (1998) Critical thinking in a distributed environment: A pedagogical base for the design of conferencing systems C.J. Bonk, K.S. King (Eds.), *Electronic collaborators: Learner-centered technologies for literacy, apprenticeship, and discourse*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahwah, NJ, 51-78
- Dyrbye, L., Cumyn, A., Day, H., & Heflin, M. (2009). A qualitative study of physicians' experiences with online learning in a masters degree program: Benefits, challenges, and proposed solutions. *Medical teacher*, 31(2), e40-e46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590802366129>
- Fish, L. A. (2016). A Preliminary Study of Changes in Online Graduate Business Student Perceptions Over a Course. *Business Education Innovation Journal*, 8(2). http://www.beijournal.com/images/V8N2_85.pdf
- Fish, W., & Gill, P. (2009). Perceptions of online instruction. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(1).
- Frith, K. H., 2002. Effect of conversation on nursing student outcomes in a Web-based course on cardiac rhythm interpretation. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Georgia State University, Atlanta.
- George PP, Papachristou N, Belisario JM, Wang W, Wark PA, Cotic Z, et al. Online eLearning for undergraduates in health professions: a systematic review of the impact on knowledge, skills, attitudes and satisfaction. *Journal of Global Health*. 2014; 4(1):010406. <https://doi.org/10.7189/jogh.04.010406>
- Hadijah, S., & Shalawati, S. (2017). Investigating Teacher 'Barrier to ICT Integration in Teaching English at Senior High School in Pekanbaru. *Proceedings of ISELT FBS Universitas Negeri Padang*, 302. <http://ejournal.unp.ac.id/index.php/selt/article/view/8019>
- Hamed, M. (2021) "The Experiences, Challenges, and Acceptance of e-Learning as a Tool for Teaching during the COVID-19 Pandemic among University Medical Staff." *PLoS One*, vol. 16, no. 3, Public Library of Science, p. e0248758
- Hartmann, S., Braae, L., Pedersen, S., & Khalid, M. (2017). The potentials of using cloud computing in schools: A systematic literature review. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 16(1), 190-202.
- Harvey, H. L., Parahoo, S., & Santally, M. (2017). Should gender differences be considered when assessing student satisfaction in the online learning environment for millennials? *Higher Education Quarterly*, 71(2), 141-158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12116>
- Hay, A. Hodgkinson, M. Peltier, J.W. & Drago, W.A. (2004) Interaction and virtual learning. *Strategic Change*, 13 (4), 193-201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsc.679>
- Hechter, R., & Vermette, L. (2013). Technology integration in K-12 science classrooms: An analysis of

- barriers and implications. *Themes in Science & Technology Education*, 6(2), 73-90. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/148638/>
- Hens, N., Ayelel, G. M., Goeyvaerts, Marc Aerts, M., Mossong, J, Edmunds, J. W and Philippe Beutels (2009) Estimating the impact of school closure on social mixing behaviour and the transmission of close contact infections in eight European countries. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 9:187 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2334-9-187>
- Henson, S.W. Kennett, P.A. & Kennedy, K.N. (2003). Web-based cases in strategic marketing *Journal of Marketing Education*, 25 (3), 250-259. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0273475303257554>
- Horspool, A., & Lange, C. (2012). Applying the scholarship of teaching and learning: student perceptions, behaviours and success online and face-to-face. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 37(1), 73-88. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2010.49653>
- Hurmerinta-Peltomaki, L., & Nummela, N. (2006). Mixed methods in international business research: A value-added perspective. *Management International Review*, 46(4), 439-459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11575-006-0100-z>
- Jacob, U. S & Pillay, J (2021) Impact of Virtual Learning Space in Teaching Learners with Moderate Intellectual Disability. *Psychology and education*, 57(9), 1120 – 1126 <http://psychologyandeducation.net/pae/index.php/pae/article/view/417/2540>
- Kamble, A., Gauba, R., Desai, S. & Golhar, D. (2021). Learners' Perception of the Transition to Instructor-Led Online Learning Environments: Facilitators and Barriers During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 22(1), 199–215. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v22i1.4971>
- Kokko, T., Pesonen, H., Kontu, E., & Pirttimaa, R. (2015). Why Study Online in Upper Secondary School? Qualitative Analysis of Online Learning Experiences. *Human Technology: An Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments*, 11, 57-70. <https://doi.org/10.17011/ht/urn.201505061740>
- Little-Wiles, J., Eugenia F., Patricia F. "Understanding gender differences in online learning." In 2014 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE) Proceedings, pp. 1- 4. IEEE, (2014)
- Mahyoob, M (2020) Challenges of e-Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic Experienced by EFL Learners. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)* 11(4) Pp. 351-362 DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no4.23>
- Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., & Jones, K. (2009). Evaluation of evidence-based practices in online learning (NED Publication Number ED-04-CO-0040). U.S. Department of Education. <http://www.ed.gov/rschstat/eval/tech/evidence-based-practices/finalreport.pdf>
- Mills, D.Q. & Salloway, M. (2001) Web-supported interaction in an MBA course *Educause Quarterly*, 24 (2), 56-59 <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/92859/>
- Muller D, Parkas V, Amiel J, Anand S, (2020) Cassese T, Cunningham T, et al. Guiding principles for undergraduate medical education in the time of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Med Teach*. 3; 1–5.
- Muilenburg, L. Y., & Berge, Z. L. (2005). Student barriers to online learning: A factor analytic study. *Distance Education*, 26(1), 29-48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587910500081269>
- Murphy, K.L. & Collins, M.P. (1997) Communication conventions in instructional electronic chats *First Monday*, 2 (11) https://www.firstmonday.dk/issues/issues2_11/index.html
- National Centre for Vocational Education Research (2002) Flexibility through online learning: At glance National Centre for Vocational Education Research, Australia <https://www.voiced.edu.au/content/ngv:42008>
- Navarro, P. (2000). The promise—and potential pitfalls—of cyberlearning. In R. A. Cole (Ed.), *Issues in web-based pedagogy: A critical primer* (pp. 281-297). Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Nistor, N. (2013). Stability of attitudes and participation in online university courses: Gender and location effects. *Computers & Education*, 68, 284–292.
- O'Cathain, A., Murphy, E., & Nicholl, J. (2010). Three techniques for integrating data in mixed methods studies. *Bmj*, 341. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.c4587>
- Oliver, R. (2001). Assuring the quality of online learning in Australian higher education. *Proceedings of Moving Online II Conference*, 2001, 222–231.
- Petrides, L.A. (2002) Web-based technologies for distributed (or distance) learning: Creating learning-centered educational experiences in the higher education classroom *International Journal of Instructional Media*, 29 (1), 69-77
- Platt, C. A., Raile, A., & Yu, N. (2014). Virtually the same? Student perceptions of the equivalence of online classes vs. face-to-face classes. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 10, 489-494. https://jolt.merlot.org/vol10no3/Platt_0914.pdf
- Picciano, A.G. (2002). Beyond student perceptions: Issues of interaction, presence, and performance in an online course *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 6 (1), 21-40 <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.98.6506&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

- Poole, D.M. (2000). Student participation in a discussion-oriented online course: A case study *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 33 (2), 162-177
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08886504.2000.10782307>
- Quadri, N. N., Muhammed, A., Sanober, S., Qureshi, M., & Shah, A. (2017). Barriers Affecting Successful Implementation of E-Learning in Saudi Arabian Universities. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 107. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v12i06.7003>
- Scheier, M. F., & Carver, C. S. (2009). Optimism. In S.J. Lopez (Ed.), *The encyclopedia of positive psychology* (pp. 656-663). Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Scheier, M. F., Carver, C. S., & Bridges, M. W. (2001). Optimism, pessimism, and psychological well-being. In E. C. Chang (Ed.), *Optimism and pessimism: Implications for theory, research, and practice* (pp. 189-216). Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Schrum L. (2002). Oh, what wonders you will see: Distance education past, present, and future. *Learning and Leading with Technology*, 30 (3)
- Simamora, R. M. (2020). The Challenges of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: An essay analysis of performing arts education students. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 1(2), 86-103. <https://doi.org/10.46627/silet.v1i2.38>
- Simonson, M., Smaldino, S., Albright, M., & Zvacek, S. (2009). *Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education* (4th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2011.589757>
- Singh V, Thurman A. (2019) How many ways can we define online learning? A systematic literature review of definitions of online learning (1988–2018). *American Journal of Distance Education* 33(4):289–306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2019.1663082>
- Smart, K., & J. Cappel, J. (2006). Students' perceptions of online learning: A comparative study. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 5, 201–219. <https://doi.org/10.28945/243>
- Wang S, Dai M. (2020) Status and situation of postgraduate medical students in China under the influence of COVID-19. *postgraduate medical journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-020-137763>
- Vonderwell, S. (2003). An examination of asynchronous communication experiences and perspectives of students in an online course: A case study. *Internet and Higher Education*, 6, 77-90. [http://anitacrawley.net/Resources/Articles/Vonderwell\(2003\).pdf](http://anitacrawley.net/Resources/Articles/Vonderwell(2003).pdf)
- Wali, A., & Omaid, M. (2020). The Use of Smartphones as an Educational Tool in the Classroom: Lecturers' Perceptions. *International Journal Of Emerging Technologies In Learning (IJET)*, 15(16), 238–247. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i16.14179>.
- Wu, V., Yen, L., & Marek, M. (2011). Using online EFL interaction to increase confidence, motivation, and ability. *Educational Technology & Society*, 14(3), 118-129. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ963205>
- Yukselturk, E. & Bulut, S. (2007). Predictors for Student Success in an Online Course. *Educational Technology & Society*, 10 (2), 71-83. <http://anitacrawley.net/Resources/Articles/Yukselturk.pdf>
- Yusoff, N. L. (2008) *Virtual Learning Space for Kindergarten* Dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor of Technology (Hons) (Business Information System)

Author Information

Udeme Samuel Jacob

Postdoctoral Research Fellow, South African Research Chair in Education and Care in Childhood, Faculty of Education, University of Johannesburg, South Africa

Jace Pillay

South African Research Chair in Education and Care in Childhood, Faculty of Education, University of Johannesburg, South Africa

Bolanle Misitura Oyundoyin

Department of Home Science and Management, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta. Ogun State

John Olusegun Oyundoyin

Department of Special Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria
